

The Challenges of Bioeconomy and Strategies to Sustainable Development in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Bioeconomy has been proposed as a strategy to overcome many global and national challenges, from climate action to income diversification.. Therefore, the ultimate goal is not to measure the bioeconomy per se, but its sustainability. The world faces multiple challenges: climate change, food security, loss of biodiversity, and rural poverty. Several new technological strategies have been introduced to address climate change. Nigeria faces several sustainable development challenges. One major challenge is the need for effective policy implementation, which is hindered by issues such as corruption, bad leadership, political instability, slow public service structures, and ethnicity. Important element of a comprehensive adaptation framework is the development of the bioeconomy. This paper focuses on challenges of bioeconomy and strategy for a sustainable development in Nigeria. It highlights and identifies the current state of bioeconomy and how bioeconomy opportunities might develop and be supported towards achieving sustainable development in Nigeria. At the initial stage, bioeconomy was associated with the dynamic development and achievements in the fields of biology and biotechnology before being linked with environment, ecological development, and sustainability. Bioeconomy has gained significant attention in recent years, with countries adopting it to drive their developmental efforts. However, the concept has not been adequately examined and integrated into policy making in Nigeria. This paper provides an overview of bioeconomy in terms of motivation, policy framework, and application as a concept for achieving sustainable development.

Key Words: *Challenges, Bioeconomy, Strategies, Sustainable, Development, Nigeria*

INTRODUCTION

Over the past 20 years, the value of the sustainable and circular bioeconomy in transforming the economy across all sectors has become more recognized globally. It arises from different types of biological innovations and protects and regenerates renewable natural resources, providing local, regional, social and economic development opportunities. It provides essential building blocks for strategies to address climate change mitigation and adaptation and nature loss, more broadly. This promotes job creation, safeguards livelihoods and secures future health and food supply. It is cross-sectoral, systemic and emergent in nature, and thus has a multi-faceted impact benefiting the economy, society and environment. The bio economy in Nigeria is a rapidly growing sector that has the potential to drive economic growth, create jobs, and improve the country's food security. The bio-economy is based on the sustainable use of biological resources, such as crops, forests, and oceans, to produce food, energy, and other products. (De Besi, & McCormick, 2023).

The bioeconomy can be defined as “the production, utilization and conservation of biological resources, including related knowledge, science, technology, and innovation, to provide information, products, processes and services across all economic sectors aiming toward a sustainable economy. The bioeconomy is widely understood as an economic system that combines in a synergic way both natural resources and technologies, together with markets, people and policies. There are established links between old industries traditionally based on natural resources and new ones those previously had no direct relations. Bioeconomy, according to the Global Bioeconomy Summit (2020), is the conservation, production, utilization, and regeneration of bio resources, in addition to allied technologies, science, knowledge, and innovation to proffer lasting solutions across and within all economic sectors, and facilitate a transformation to a sustainable economy. Advocates of the bioeconomy concept anticipate that biotechnology will make major contributions to its development via innovations in deriving products and energy from renewable biomass (Bracco et al., 2018, Befort, 2020).

In line with their respective political pursuits, the US, the EU, and several international bodies have individually designed comprehensive blueprints and adopted the bioeconomy as a viable approach for unlocking new prospects for economic development and innovation, as well as achieving the sustainable development goals (SDGs) (FAO, 2018, Heimann, 2019, Pandey, 2021). While South Africa boasts of a clearly defined bioeconomy plan, Nigeria is still lagging behind, despite an abundance of biomass resources. (Devaney, & Henchion, 2017).

Bioeconomy is credited as being one of the key pillars for the FAO Strategic Framework 2022–2031 to support the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals. More than 60 countries and regions have a dedicated bioeconomy or bioscience strategy today, and many more are already implementing the bioeconomy with plans and programmes, often also attempting to monitor and evaluate the progress towards the transition. Moreover, where trade-offs exist between different sustainability objectives, the bioeconomy offers an opportunity to realign the economy with the biosphere and account for the trade-offs in a holistic way. This aligns with FAO’s strategic mission over the next decade; FAO is the first United Nations entity to elevate bioeconomy to a corporate priority, including it as one of 20 programme priority areas under its Strategic Framework 2022–2031. This reflects the growing role that FAO sees bioeconomy as a driver of sustainable agrifood systems transformation over the next decade. (Oguntuase, 2023).

It drew from international experiences in implementing bioeconomy to provide lessons that Nigerian stakeholders can use to develop and implement a comprehensive bioeconomy policy framework to solve environmental and societal challenges. However, bioeconomy has become the center of sustainable economic strategies in numerous countries but Nigeria lacks a cohesive bioeconomy policy. The chief motivation for bioeconomy adoption in these countries is to address societal challenges while achieving sustainable economic development. The policies focused on research and innovation, education and training, stakeholders' engagement, technology transfer, commercialisation, and market development support. In order to achieve sustainable development, Nigeria must develop and implement a holistic bioeconomy policy cutting across all relevant economic sectors. (Philp, 2017).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Framework

Conceptions of a bioeconomy emerged in the 20th century, it was not until the 21st century that the concept started attracting great interest from scientists and politicians; shaping development strategies. The bioeconomy is increasingly recognized as a key concept in making the transition to a sustainable and inclusive future. Further momentum has been gained at the international level since the 3rd Global Bioeconomy Summit held in November 2020. For example, China, the USA, ASEAN and East Africa and some LATAM countries have adopted new innovative and bold bioeconomy strategies. The 27 Member States of the European Union have recently adopted Council Conclusions on the bioeconomy. The FAO has included a bioeconomy pillar in its Strategic Framework 2022-31. The relevance of the bioeconomy in climate change is increasingly acknowledged in global fora, including the recent COP15 global agreement on biodiversity and ecosystems services. IACGB acknowledges and encourages global discussions on the critical factors that support a successful journey to a sustainable transformation of the economy.

The concept has gained scientific and political attention during the recent years, especially in Nigeria but also globally. From the review and analysis of the literature, this paper addresses the emerging bioeconomy, definitions and conceptual bases, and its great potential in different sectors of economic activity and development of new products. Countries and regions around the world face a number of economic, environmental and social challenges. Increased demand for energy, primary resources (agricultural, forestry and fishing), industrial products and services (healthcare in particular) put significant pressure on the sustainability of the ecosystems that support our society. One option to provide a more sustainable base for the economy would be the transition towards bioeconomy in which the importance of biotechnology and biomass-based production to generate economic output is significantly greater than today. Bioeconomy is considered to encompass all economic activity connected with the utilization of renewable biological resources. (Bugge, Hansen, Klitkou, 2024).

Bioeconomy has gained traction among scientists and policy makers to shape developmental efforts in many developed countries, such as Germany, France, Finland, Sweden, Belgium, The Netherlands, Russia, Malaysia, and Japan, among others. Only South Africa has published an official bioeconomy strategy in Africa. The next wave of economy is bioeconomy, which produces economic growth and wellbeing. Already many developed and developing countries are placing emphasis on the development of a bioeconomy, Nigeria and other African countries must not be

left behind. To advance a sustainable bioeconomy in Nigeria, this paper calls for the development of a holistic bioeconomy policy which must be an integral part of the national developmental agenda.

A responsible bioeconomy sector for Nigeria calls for effective governance and coordination to make it cut across all the relevant economic sectors. Enhancing a competitive and productive bioeconomy requires target investment in research, innovation and skills; education and training; policy interaction and stakeholders engagement; market development support to enhance competitiveness; and demand side instruments while taking into account legitimate societal concerns and needs. With appropriate political commitment across all arms of the federation, Nigeria could embrace bioeconomy to overcome a number of her environmental, social and economic challenges. (Abass, 2023).

It is clear that Nigeria must set its own bioeconomy agenda, consistent with its local conditions, capacities, and needs. The key is to identify possibilities and opportunities, with the involvement of different sectors of society and stakeholders. A dedicated national bioeconomy policy cutting cross multiple natural resource sectors and industries, connecting up biological resource sectors and existing ideas and innovation for optimum value chain development, will help achieve sustainability and prosperity.

The 2020 Communiqué furthermore urged the strengthening of actions for creating global bioeconomy policies. These included: Capitalizing on the power of science and technology, creating bioeconomy jobs through partnerships and innovation, mobilizing finance for bioeconomy development, increasing involvement of industry and business, promoting resilient value chains, strengthening demand side policy approaches, promoting partnership, shared responsibilities and a global platform.

The Communiqué from GBS 2015 outlined cornerstones of a global agenda, together with policy measures, leading to a sustainable bioeconomy. The Communiqué in 2018 stressed the importance of the social impact of a bioeconomy and the Communiqué issued from GBS2020 specifically emphasized the bioeconomy's role in the transformation of industry. The IACGB recognizes that the role of the bioeconomy in 2023 is advancing in providing sustainable solutions for global challenges. Building on the priorities and recommendations of the 2020 Communiqué, the IACGB acknowledges the achievements since 2020 and revisits the milestones and goals. (Henchion, et al. 2024).

Bioeconomy Strategies and Sustainability

Developing regional and national bioeconomy strategies is an important step in developing Africa's bioeconomy. South Africa is the only country in Africa that has implemented a comprehensive strategy. While new technologies and changing socio-economic patterns of production and consumption can be a force for good, they can also pose considerable risks. It is therefore essential to keep developments in the bioeconomy within ecological limits, and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) are the most important global expression of the sustainability imperative. Early research indicates that most countries with a political bioeconomy strategy have neither identified any conflicting goals between achieving the SDGs and fostering the bioeconomy nor addressed them through regulatory frameworks. (Dubois, & San Juan. 2022).

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It is especially important to do so in a continent that in general has relatively abundant natural resources, and where governance can be relatively weak. It is also important to introduce better regulatory safeguards for socio-ecological sustainability, while at the same time ensuring that economic growth and development are not stalled in the process. Participants identified actions and recommendations for an agenda for the African bioeconomy that can support the SDGs. We summarise the key points below:

Create jobs through bio-based economic growth. Develop policies and regulatory frameworks that create demand for bio-based technologies and knowledge, as well as on certification, quality and environmental standards, public procurement efforts and tax incentives.

Drive innovation. There is a need to link innovation to market actors and translate promising technologies and expertise into societal benefits on a large scale. African countries often need support to build capacity in the public R&D sectors, including training in entrepreneurship and platforms for communication to enable academia to better interact with market actors. The European Commission already contributes tailor-made policy initiatives and sustainable joint research and investment projects Such as the EU Bio-based Industries Joint Undertaking, a €3.7 billion partnership between the EU and the Bio-based Industries Consortium.

Link African farmers to markets and agro-value chains to gain benefit from bioeconomy developments. Diverse and resource-efficient agro-processing, agro-waste and biomass value chains are central to an African bioeconomy, and to enable African farmers and biomass producers to diversify their production and connect to local, regional and international markets. Countries should promote integrated agro-industrial parks and bio business incubating services, encompassing the whole of the value chain from the farm to the processing centre. Existing initiatives include the **Ethiopian Investment Commission**, which aims to set up 14 agro-industrial parks in the country by 2025. However, it is important not to underestimate the importance of local and small-scale everyday bioeconomy activity. (Ipate David, Ipate, & Bogdan, 2023).

Support African bio-based companies: a strong and engaged African private sector in particular, small to medium enterprises (SMEs) – are crucial for translating the promises of the bioeconomy into usable tools for practitioners, not least for smallholder farmers. The problem is that in most African countries the private sector lacks the capacity and resources to move research and development efforts to market, often because there is limited collaboration between innovators within Africa's SMEs and knowledge producers. Investment and support to enable SME's to deploy modern bioeconomy technologies to the African market are therefore crucial. One of the many recommendations for driving the bioeconomy in Africa is to link African farmers to markets and agro-value chains to gain benefit from bioeconomy developments.

Assess and address tensions and potential conflicts. Potential resource conflicts in the emerging African bioeconomy revolve around biomass production for food versus other products, socioeconomic challenges, and small-scale vs large-scale biomass production. African countries also need to effectively evaluate risks and benefits associated with new biosciences, biomass

bioresource vision and bio-ecology vision. These ideal type of visions of the bioeconomy are not mutually exclusive and overlap. (Fenton, Fenelon, Finn et al. 2017). In contrast, a bio-resource vision provides for a broader definition, which may include some or all of the following: agriculture, forestry, food, timber, chemical, pharmaceutical and energy industries (Meyer, 2017). The bio-technology vision and bio-resources vision emphasize the technological dimension and the role of research, development and innovation (RDI) aligned with the Nigerian National Biotechnology Policy and the National Science Technology and Innovation Policy. The prominence of technology in bio-technology vision and bio-resources vision could imply a business as usual ‘trajectory.

It also could mean that strategies that follow such a vision give limited attention to changing consumer behaviour and reducing the demand for biobased products as a mechanism to transition to a more sustainable economy. The bio-ecology vision has developed in response to criticisms of bioeconomy strategies and also to provide a fundamental alternative to the dominance of industrialized agriculture. While economic growth and employment creation is a main concern in the bio-technology and bio-resource visions, these aspects are clearly secondary to sustainability concerns in the bio-ecology vision (Henchion et al. 2017; Levidow, Birch, & Papaioannou, 2013; Meyer, 2017).

Some combination of more than one vision, centered on a bioresources vision, is likely to be appropriate for Nigeria. It is important to map the state of the bioeconomy in Nigeria, anticipate its evolution, review existing polices and regulatory requirements, research and technological capabilities, training and skill needs, bespoke natural resources (biomass and marine) availability, demographics and consumer preferences, factor in views of relevant stakeholders, markets, historical legacies and other relevant issues.(Dubois, & San Juan, 2022).

Bioeconomy could help Nigeria transform from a fossil dependent and resource-based agriculture to knowledge-based value chain economy. According Euapermkiati (2017) the two key elements to achieve this transformation are modern farming and bio refinery. Modern farming requires improved breeding, provision of machineries and development of technologies on agricultural products. Investment in bio refinery helps to produce food, feed, bioenergy, biochemical and pharmaceuticals. Establishing bio refinery complexes in existing industrial parks in the country will be an added advantage.

More recently, the European Commission (2018) defined the bioeconomy as an economy that uses renewable biological resources from the land and sea (e.g., animals, crops, fish, forests and microorganisms) to produce energy, food and materials (D’Adamo et al., 2022). Modern bioeconomy should not focus only on biomass and substitution of fossil fuels with sustainable and renewable alternatives, but should be targeted towards “biologisation” of the economy via disruptive innovations that convert bioresources into food, feed, products, and services that integrate sustainability (Global Bioeconomy Summit, 2020).

Globally, over 50 countries now have bioeconomy-related initiatives (Aguilar et al., 2019). In 2014, about USD 2 trillion worth of bio-based foods, fuels, and products were shipped, accounting for 13% of global commerce, up from 10% in 2007 (El-Chichakli et al., 2016). Many poor and middle-income nations are beginning to adopt the bioeconomy as an approach to unlock new prospects for economic growth and for achieving the United Nations’ SDGs (FAO, 2018). A

sustainable bioeconomy therefore must emphasize the use of resources as long and as efficiently as possible, with minimal or reused waste, leading to the concept of a “circular bioeconomy” (CE) (Stratan, 2017, Ranjbari et al., 2022). The recognition that the bioeconomy is to a great degree coupled to circularity was reinforced by the concept of “circular bioeconomy” (CBE). This laid the foundation for the European Commission’s vision of the bioeconomy, which incorporates the idea of renewability, sustainability, and circularity, with a view to cut back on waste, while advancing towards a closed-loop economy (Ranjbari et al., 2022).

Policy makers in the European Union (EU) have tipped the concept of sustainable development and CBE as high priority models that can expedite the attainment of the United Nations sustainable development goals (SDGs) (Kardung et al., 2021, D’Adamo and Sassanelli, 2022). The CBE or bio-based CE is built around the efficient and sustainable valorization of biomass (Ranjbari et al., 2022) via integrated and multiple product production chains, while utilizing waste and optimizing biomass value over time through cascades (Rodríguez, 2022). Being a carbon neutral renewable energy source of plant or animal origin, biomass has been widely investigated by scholars within the context of the establishment of a CE and CBE. Consequently, a broad knowledge by key players of the benefits of biomass utility and its implications along the entire value chain is a prerequisite for a successful transition towards a CBE (Ranjbari et al., 2022). Bio refineries, which are facilities for transforming different biomass feedstock to a sundry of high premium bio-based products are pivotal to the establishment of the bioeconomy (Ranjbari et al., 2022). The generation of biofuels and other materials from food waste-based bio refineries has been touted as an avenue to combat the problems of resource scarcity, climate change, price volatility and increasing demand (Ranjbari et al., 2022). By incorporating waste engineering processes into city designing, Europe’s HOOP project is converting urban bio-waste and wastewater into bio-based products, and transforming cities into urban CBE centers (Global Bioeconomy Summit, 2020).

According to a recent analysis, Nigeria earned more revenue from non-oil sources in 2016, which amounted to NGN 602.19 billion (53% of total revenue) than it did from oil earnings of NGN 433 billion (47% of total revenue) for the first time since 1971 (Burns and Owen, 2019). Many studies have already identified Nigeria’s emerging shift away from oil as its political and economic base, pointing to a swiftly approaching post-oil future. Few recognize, however, that this future has already occurred; Nigeria is and has been in a post-oil era for some years (Burns and Owen, 2019). The implication of this is that, as Nigeria attempts to diversify its economy, it would witness a much lesser dependence on the oil sector and create more employment (Obembe, 2021). As such, a knowledge-driven, and sustainable bioeconomy has a major role to play in this regard.

EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Bioeconomy is considered to be an alternative economic model to our present fossil-dependent model which is based on high consumptions of rare materials, often low economic returns, and extensive consumption of natural and labor resources (Ionesco, 2013). As a new wave of economic system, the bioeconomy combines in a synergic way both natural resources and technologies, together with markets, people and policies to provide a solid and realistic foundation for achieving the sustainability need worldwide (Maciejczak, 2017).

Ndubuisi-Okolo & Anekwe (2018) studied strategies for Achieving Sustainable Development in Nigeria: The study adopted a conceptual approach in an attempt to x-ray the various strategies for achieving sustainable development in Nigeria. The strategies enumerated include but not limited to the following factors: Poverty alleviation, youth empowerment, entrepreneurship education and effective leadership. Materials for the study were gathered via internet, textbooks, and other documents relevant to the study. The findings based on the literature reviewed indicate that sustainable development is achievable only when social, economic, political and environmental sustainability elements in Nigeria are stable, viable and equitable. The study also recommended that the federal, state and local government should ensure that funds allotted to them are properly disbursed to the concerned groups.

Akintoye & Opeyemi (2014), studied the prospects for achieving Sustainable Development through the Millennium Development Goals in Nigeria. The study was carried out with a view to enhance the understanding about the analytical content of sustainable development as well as sensitizing the Nigerian economy to key into the current wave of sustaining the global economy. A review of the plan implementation of the World Summit on Sustainable Development was carried out by the study vis-à-vis the Nigerian economy. In the light of the findings of the study, considering some of the environmental as well as socio- economic challenges permeating the Nigerian economy, the study concluded that the Nigerian government should concentrate on key areas that can help boost and sustain its development objectives. (Sillanpää, & Ncibi, 2019)

Ogbo, Eneh-Nnaji for, Agbaeze, Chukwu & Isigola (2017) studied the strategies for achieving sustainable economy in Nigeria taking into consideration the acceptable stakeholders. The work looks at the explosion of the Nigerian population from the year 2005 to date; the modern state of the Nigerian economy and the failed strategies tried in the past, with a look at the acceptable stakeholders, sustainable economy, and the strategic priorities to be considered in the Nigerian context. Theories of modernization (showing the five take off stages), sustainable development and human development (with the five key capitals) were used to analyze the problem of achieving a sustainable economy in Nigeria. The triple-bottom-line strategy was seen to be a possible solution to the impending problem of unstable economy in Nigeria, intending to social responsibility, environmental protection, and economic priority. (Pfau, Hagens, Dankbaar, & Smits, 2023)

Pfau, Hagens, Dankbaar, & Smits (2014) submitted that bioeconomy cannot be considered as self-evidently sustainable, sustainability has been and will continue to be an inherent characteristic of bioeconomy, serving as a basis for a more interdisciplinary or trans-disciplinary way of approaching bioeconomy. Bioeconomy has drawn attention to the need to strengthen the meaning of the term sustainable development. Ramcilovik-Suominen and Helga (2018) believed that the way bioeconomy polices perceive sustainability and sustainable development as concepts will have profound implications not only on a practical level for policy implementation, but also on a conceptual level and for theoretical discourse surrounding sustainable development. The future of sustainable development is the implementation of bioeconomy strategies to prevent urgent problems, such as increasing competition. (McDonagh, 2024).

Ogbo, et al. (2017) focused on the strategies for achieving sustainable economy in Nigeria taking into consideration the acceptable stakeholders. This work looks at the explosion of the Nigerian population from the year 2005 till date, the modern state of the Nigerian economy and the failed

strategies adopted in the past, with a critical look at the acceptable stakeholders, sustainable economy, and the strategic priorities to be considered in the Nigerian context. Theories of modernization (showing the five take off stages), sustainable development, and human development (with the five key capitals) were used to analyze the problem of achieving a sustainable economy in Nigeria. The triple-bottom-line strategy was seen to be a possible solution to the impending problem of unstable economy in Nigeria, intending to social responsibility, environmental protection, and economic priority (Maciejczak, 2017).

Nigeria is facing a number of economic, environmental and social challenges. These challenges include unsustainable exploitation of its natural resources, unprecedented waste generation, and irreversible climate change, food, and insecurity, lack of access to energy, deforestation, soil degradation, poverty, and poor industrial production. The cross-cutting nature of bioeconomy offers a unique opportunity to address these interconnected challenges in a comprehensive manner while achieving sustainability and sustainable development (Devaney & Henchion, 2017; Dubois & San Juan 2016; Ipate et al. 2015; Maciejczak, 2017; Sillanpää & Ncibi, 2017).

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a conceptual approach in an attempt to x-ray the various strategies for achieving sustainable development in Nigeria. The justification for the adoption of this approach is because the study is exploratory in nature anchored on discovery of ideas and insights. Materials were generated via internet, textbooks and other documents relevant to this study. This is because it attempts to draw lessons from how the bioeconomy is being envisioned and applied at different levels of governance around the world. A survey was conducted to identify relevant work, Technical reports, scientific articles, and case study briefs. The studies analysed all and provide links between monitoring of a given subject of interest relevant to bioeconomy and SDGs. Although the literature on bioeconomy and related concepts and how they link to sustainability is abundant, this report limits the analysis to the literature that mentions direct links. Bioeconomy has gained significant attention in recent years, with countries adopting it to drive their developmental efforts. However, the concept has not been adequately examined and integrated into policy making in Nigeria. This paper provided an overview of bioeconomy in terms of motivation, policy framework, and application as a concept for achieving sustainable development.

The results suggested that bioeconomy monitoring and evaluation can provide opportunities to be coupled with reporting on SDGs across all three dimensions of sustainability, especially those related to economic development (e.g. SDG 8), access to food security (e.g. SDG 2), and sustainable.

CONCLUSION

However, bioeconomy has become the center of sustainable economic strategies in numerous countries but Nigeria lacks a cohesive bioeconomy policy. The chief motivation for bioeconomy adoption in these countries is to address societal challenges while achieving sustainable economic development. The policies focused on research and innovation, education and training, stakeholders' engagement, technology transfer, commercialization, and market development support. In order to achieve sustainable development, Nigeria must develop and implement a holistic bioeconomy policy cutting across all relevant economic sectors.

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RECOMMENDATION

Bioeconomy strategies developed in recent years are shaping the direction of economies and sustainability policy developments. However, the opportunities as well as the limitations of individual national/regional bioeconomy strategies and their implementation needs to be explored and discussed.

It is critically recommended to translate bioeconomy strategies and policies into actions.

- To meet global food security,
- scale bio-based products for construction, manufacturing, transportation,
- promote urban and rural economic development to address global challenges related to climate change, while reversing nature-loss and maintaining functioning ecosystems at scale.
- Sustainable sourcing and production across supply chains as well as ensuring circularity and eliminating waste as key aspects in bioeconomic solutions. •These developments need to be assessed and measured consistently; and hypotheses, barriers and drivers for the future developments need to be elaborated in a joint effort between governments, academia, the public and the private sector, both globally, regionally and locally.

The bioeconomy is increasingly proving to be a catalyst for defining future developments and influencing research, financing, and market access and consumer behavior.

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